

Kinetics and Mechanisms of Homogeneous Redox Processes Catalysed by Complex Compounds of Platinum Elements

K. B. YATSIMIRSKII

L. V. Pisarzhevsky Institute of Physical Chemistry, Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, Kiev, USSR

COMPLEX compounds of several platinum metals catalyse numerous redox processes. The catalysis is observed in the presence of extremely small quantities of platinum element compounds in solution.

If one follows the catalytic activity (the number of catalysed reactions and the catalytic coefficient) of compounds of some elements in the eighth group of the Mendeleev periodic system, it is easy to note some general tendency: in acid solutions it increases from the top to the bottom, i.e. $\text{Fe} < \text{Ru} < \text{Os}$; $\text{Co} < \text{Rh} < \text{Ir}$; $\text{Ni} < \text{Pd} < \text{Pt}$, and from the right to the left, i.e. $\text{Ni} < \text{Co} < \text{Fe}$; $\text{Pd} < \text{Rh} < \text{Ru}$; $\text{Pt} < \text{Ir} < \text{Os}$.

Many homogeneous redox processes are catalysed by osmium compounds. Compounds of ruthenium and iridium catalyse a smaller number of them and there seem only very few cases of homogeneous catalysis of redox processes by compounds of platinum, rhodium and palladium. One should think that the catalytic activity in redox processes, particularly in case of the mechanism of alternate redox process of the catalysts can be observed if the following requirements are satisfied:

- (a) the mean value of normal redox potential (about 0.8—1.0 volt),
- (b) the presence of one-electron transfers from a higher to lower oxidation state (and vice versa),
- (c) the presence of the largest possible number of vacant d-orbitals.

These requirements are most fully met by osmium, iridium and ruthenium compounds. Owing to highly unstable electron d^7 configuration palladium and platinum compounds have the oxidation state 3+ in extremely rare cases. Catalytically active rhodium

compounds seem to be characterized by rather high redox potential value.

In the course of redox reaction, electrons, or unstable particles (atoms, ions or free radicals) transfer from particle to particle. For instance, reactions between simple anions of complexes and simple ions of metals and some organic molecules, as a rule, proceed via the electron transfer mechanism. Meanwhile, the oxygen atom transfer from particle to particle takes place in the oxidation by anions of the oxygen acids or some molecular oxides¹.

The electron transfer is run either by inner or outer sphere mechanisms depending on whether the coordination spheres of complex ions are disintegrated or remained unaffected in the course of redox processes.

All inner sphere redox reactions are multistage processes, in which one of stages is rate determining.

In the simplest case, three reaction stages should be observed^{2,3,4}.

- (1) the precursor complex formation,
- (2) the electron transfer in which the precursor complex is converted into a successor complex,
- (3) the disintegration of the successor complex. In some cases, it is possible to distinguish and observe all three stages of the redox reaction.

By way of example, let us consider the paraphenitidine oxidation by vanadium(V) compounds studied together with B. Jeliaskowa^{5,6}. The reaction proceeds through three stages:

to control the reaction rate three parameters were determined :

- (1) the octet EPR signal intensity of vanadium (IV)⁻ I_V (constant increasing after an induction period is reached) ;
- (2) EPR singlet signal intensity of a *p*-phenetidine cation-radical, $-I_R$ (an increase in this value after an induction period has been attained followed by its decreasing after passing through maximum) ;
- (3) the solution optical density measured at $\lambda=553$ (D_{553}) corresponding to the light absorption by a cation-radical of *p*-phenetidine. The optical density of solution passes through maximum. In the end of the reaction the solution remains coloured because of the presence of quinone imide.

Using these three parameters (I_V , I_R and D_{553}) and the length of an induction period we could calculate the rate constants, and the concentrations of intermediate and final reaction products (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The dependence of the concentration of reaction products and optical density of solution at 560 nm on time in the interaction of vanadium(V) with *p*-phenetidine.

Reagent concentration : NH_4VO_3 — 5.34×10^{-3} M. *n*-phenetidine HCL— 8.3×10^{-2} M, *pH* 1.8, =20° . Changes in the concentrations of vanadium(IV) (1), an ion-radical, HPhen (2)⁺ precursor complex (4), and quinone imide (4), 3—the change in the optical density at 560 nm.

^x/ The ion-radicals formed converts into quinone imide as a result of fast recombination and hydrolysis.

The rate constants of the three observed reaction stages (1), (2) and (3) proved to be equal to $k_1=1.12 \times 10^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $k_2=6.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, ($k_3=1.96 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$), respectively.

The third stages appeared to be rate determining as in our case.

However, the rate determining stage can, also, be the precursor complex formation if reacting particles have like charges (electrostatic repulsion) or the coordination spheres of the both particles firmly hold out near central atoms, while an outer sphere mechanism of electron transfer is impossible.

The second stage proves to be rate determining in the presence of high potential barrier for tunnel electron transfer or electron transfer from orbital to orbital is restricted by symmetry rules

At last, as shown, the third stage can also be rate determining provided the particles, reaction products are tightly bound to each other, or the cage effect plays significant role.

In the presence of catalysts in solution, the reaction, as a rule, proceeds via new routes at higher rates of elementary stages.

Let us consider the most important redox processes in aqueous solutions catalysed by complex compounds of platinum elements.

One of the most significant, though rather simple reactions catalysed by iridium and ruthenium compounds is the oxidation of Hg_2^{2+} by cerium (IV) compounds :

The investigation of this reaction has shown that it is catalysed by iridium compounds and proceeds, at least, through three stages :

To derive a kinetic equation under steady state we used our modification of the graph method¹⁰. The concentrations of various forms (states) of a homogeneous catalyst (Ir^{III}, [Ce^{IV}...Ir^{III}], [Ce^{III}...Ir^{IV}] and Ir^{IV}) are placed at the apexes of the correspondent graph. The rates of conversion of a catalyst form into another one act as graph branches. Each branch is provided with a label corresponding to the kinetic equation for a given stage (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The topological graph corresponding to a sequence of reactions (5), (6) and (7).

The reaction route is a sequence of branches in a definite direction. The magnitude of the reaction route is equal to the product of all the branches involved. The sum total of all routes directed to a given base is called a base determinant which can be found as the product of all reaction routes directed to a given base (junction) passing only once through each apex. Parallel branches of the graph are summed up.

The homogeneous catalytic reaction rate is calculated according to the equation^{10,11,12};

$$v = \frac{C_k \sum k_i D_i}{\sum D_i} \quad (8)$$

where C_k is the total catalyst concentration (in all forms), D_i is the base determinant for an apex, k_i is the rate of an elementary stage yielding the reaction products; if a given apex is not responsible for reaction product formation, then $K_i=0$.

Fig. 2 shows the graph for a reaction sequence (5), (6) and (7). The application of equation (8) in this case allows to obtain the total reaction rate:

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [Ce^{IV}][Hg^{2+}] C_k + k_1 k_2 k_{-2} [Ce^{IV}][Ce^{III}] C_k}{k_1 k_3 [Ce^{IV}][Hg^{2+}] + k_{-2} [Ce^{IV}][Ce^{III}] + k_1 k_2 [Ce^{IV}] + k_{-1} k_3 [Hg^{2+}]} \quad (9)$$

If we neglect a second term in the numerator and the third and fourth terms in the denominator, then the equation has the following form:

$$v = \frac{k_2 k_3 [Hg^{2+}] C_k}{k_3 [Hg^{2+}] + k_{-2} [Ce^{III}]} \quad (10)$$

The equation (10) describes fairly well the experimental data, namely, the independence of the reaction rate on cerium(IV)^{x/} and mercury(II) concentrations; an initial increase in the reaction rate with the mercury(I) concentration increasing; the reaction decelerating by cerium(III) and a sharp reaction rate acceleration with the catalyst concentration growth.

Similar reaction mechanism we observe in the oxidation of mercury(I) by manganese(III) though the reaction rate in the manganese(II) oxidation by iridium(IV) was extremely low^{13,14}. The application of topological graph method allowed to establish that the reaction can be described by three stages:

The total kinetic equation of mercury(I) oxidation by manganese(III) in the presence of iridium sulphate complexes has a form:

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_3 [Mn^{III}] [Hg_2^{2+}] C_k}{k_1 [Mn^{III}] + k_3 [Hg_2^{2+}]} \quad (14)$$

Analogous mechanisms are observed in the oxidation of a variety of aromatic amines by cerium(IV) and manganese(III) compounds in the presence of iridium compounds acting as catalysts^{13,15}.

The mechanism of catalytic reactions show that ruthenium compounds are oxidized by the main oxidant to ruthenium(IV) or even(V). The whole reaction route of the oxidation of Hg_2^{2+} to Hg^{2+} in the presence of ruthenium compounds involves, at least five stages¹⁶:

^{x/} Ce(IV) in excess.

The topological graph corresponding to the scheme proposed (equations 15—19) is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The topological graph corresponding to a sequence of reactions (5), (16), (17), (18) and (19).

Using this graph and equation (3) one can obtain the kinetic equation :

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] (k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] + k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] + k_4 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]) C_K}{k_1 k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]^2 (k_1 + k_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]) + k_1 k_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] (k_1 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] + k_3 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]) + k_2 k_3 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] (k_1 + k_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}])} \quad (20)$$

It follows from equation (20) that if the concentration of cerium(III) in solution is high the reaction rate in solution must decrease.

Equation (20) can be considerably simplified, if one takes into consideration that at the beginning of the reaction Ce(III) concentration is, as a rule, small and the value of k_1 is extremely low (stage (15) practically irreversible) :

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] (k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] + k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]) C_K}{k_1 k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]^2 + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]} \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) can further be simplified at small concentrations of mercury(I), $k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \gg k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$:

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] C_K}{k_1 k_1 k_5 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]^2 + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]} \quad (22)$$

This equation accounts for a decrease in the reaction rate in the presence of mercury(I) compounds in a great excess.

An analogous mechanism of the catalysis by ruthenium compounds seems to take place also in the diphenylamine oxidation by cerium(IV)¹⁷. One can believe that the catalysis by ruthenium compounds of the hydrazine oxidation by cerium(IV) compounds also proceeds via the alternate redox mechanism of ruthenium(III,IV) sulphate complexes¹⁸.

The fact that ruthenium (III,IV) compounds catalyse the oxidation of aromatic amines by manganese(III) compounds in acid solution¹⁹ speaks in favour of the proposed mechanism.

The data considered allow to express some general ideas on reasons and mechanism of catalytic action of coordination compounds of platinum metals in the oxidation of cationoid (Hg_2^{2+}) and some other reductants having either positive (protonated amine forms) or neutral molecules by cationoid oxidants (cerium(IV) and manganese(III) compounds).

The coordination compounds of platinum elements discussed here are, as a rule, anions and, therefore, can interact directly with positively charged particles of oxidants and reductants. Thus, in the presence of a majority of catalyst complexes the electrostatic repulsion restriction seems to be removed.

The redox processes considered here must be spin restricted due to the appearance of the two paramagnetic particles as a result of one electron transfer from reductants to oxidants :

Restriction by spin is known to be less strict in the presence of spin-orbit interaction well-defined (in the coordination compounds of platinum metals which increases) in the elements of the eighth group of periodic system from the top to the bottom.

To make a catalytic redox process possible it is necessary to meet the main thermodynamic requirement, namely, the normal redox potentials of the pair : catalyst (oxydized form)—catalyst (reduced form) must have an intermediate value between the redox potentials of main oxidants and reductants.

Normal redox potential values of catalytically active coordination compounds of platinum elements as mentioned above are about 1 volt. Hence, the catalysis by coordination compounds of platinum elements can be observed in the interaction between

oxidants having normal potentials exceeding 1 volt and reductants with normal potentials which are less than 1 volt. Table 1 lists some redox (potential) pairs that meet these requirements. Normal potential for some compounds of platinum elements are given, too.

Rather unstable, rapidly reacting oxidants and reductants (permanganate, simple metal ions, etc) are not included in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that the number of oxidants and reductants the reactions of which can be catalysed by complex compounds of platinum elements is rather large.

In the presence of cerium compounds as an oxidant the reduction can be effected by arsenic(III) compounds. The reaction is catalysed by osmium compounds. Osmium displays oxidation states from 8+ to 4+ in turn and vice versa depending on the reaction conditions (reagent concentration, the reagent ratio, etc)²⁰.

The oxidation states 8+, 7+, 6+ seem to be observed in the hydrazine oxidation by vanadium(V) catalysed by osmium compounds²¹.

Table 1 shows that anions of oxygen acid halogens (IO₄⁻, IO₃⁻, BrO₃⁻, ClO₃⁻ etc), may act as oxidants. The reaction proceeds in this case either through an electron transfer from reductant to oxidant or transfer of atoms (for instance, oxygen) or a group of atoms¹ from oxidant to reductant. In oxygen atom transfer from oxidant to reductant the oxidation state is immediately changed by two units. One may think, for example, that the oxidation of osmium(VI) to (VIII) by bromate occurs by an oxygen atom transfer.

We have studied the oxidation of *p*-phenetidine by bromate in the presence of osmium compounds²². It has been established that catalytically active osmium compounds proved to be in the oxidation states 8+ and 6+, and not in the oxidation state 4+, perhaps due to low solubility of OsO₂.

The oxidation of iodide by the periodate-ion in acid medium is catalysed by ruthenium and iridium compounds. One may suppose²³, that as a result of addition of one electron from a reductant at the first stage, the periodate-ion in aqueous solution converts into a radical-like species, IO₃[·], which on addition of the second electron turns into an anion, IO₃⁻. In the same two-stage process the I⁻ anion converts into

a molecule, I₂. The kinetics of first stage (more precise the sum of the first two stages) of this catalytic reaction has been studied :

The kinetics of iodide oxidation by hexachloroiridate has also been investigated²³

TABLE 1. NORMAL REDOX POTENTIALS OF OXIDANTS, REDUCTANTS AND CATALYSTS

Redox system	Normal potential
<i>Oxidants</i>	
Ce(IV) + e ⇌ Ce(III)	1.44-1.7 ^{x/}
Mn ³⁺ + e ⇌ Mn ²⁺	1.51
IO ₄ ⁻ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⇌ IO ₃ ⁻ + H ₂ O	1.8
BrO ₃ ⁻ + 6H ⁺ + 6e ⇌ Br ⁻ + 3 H ₂ O	1.44
ClO ₃ ⁻ + 6H ⁺ + 6e ⇌ Cl ⁻ + 3 H ₂ O	1.45
H ₂ O ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⇌ 2 H ₂ O	1.77
<i>Reductants</i>	
2 Hg ²⁺ + 2e ⇌ Hg ₂ ²⁺	0.91
H ₃ AsO ₄ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⇌ HAsO ₂ + 2 H ₂ O	0.56
I ₂ + 2 e ⇌ 2 I ⁻	0.53
X + ne = amine	0.5-0.8
<i>Catalysts</i>	
OsO ₄ + 2 e ⇌ OsO ₄ ²⁻	0.3
OsO ₄ ²⁻ + 2 H ₂ O + 2e ⇌ OsO ₂ + 4 OH ⁻	0.1
OsO ₄ + 6 Cl ⁻ + 8H ⁺ + 4e ⇌ OsCl ₆ ²⁻ + 4 H ₂ O	1.0
RuCl ₆ OH ²⁻ + H ⁺ + e ⇌ RuCl ₆ ²⁻ + H ₂ O	1.3 ^{xx/}
IrCl ₆ ²⁻ + e ⇌ IrCl ₆ ³⁻	1.02
RhCl ₆ ²⁻ + e ⇌ RhCl ₆ ³⁻	1.2
RhO ₂ + 4 H ⁺ + 6Cl ⁻ + e ⇌ RhCl ₆ ³⁻ + 2 H ₂ O	1.4

x/ The potential value depends on medium (HClO₄, HNO₃ or H₂SO₄).

xx/ The potential value of Ru(IV)-Ru(III) in H₂SO₄ is considered to be about 1.0-1.2.

The results of more thorough investigation show that anions of the IrCl_6^{2-} type display very low catalytic activity. The catalytic activity drastically increases in slow hydrolysis of chloride complexes, i.e. the catalysis is effected by species of the $[\text{IrCl}_{6-n}(\text{OH})_n]^{2-}$ type.

This phenomenon was used to study equilibriums of the type²⁴

Table 2 presents the data obtained.

TABLE 2. EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF FORMATION OF $[\text{IrCl}_n(\text{OH})_{7-n}]^{2-}$ x/ COMPLEXES AND TURNOVER NUMBERS IN THE OXIDATION OF IODIDE BY PERIODATE

Iridium complexes	Equilibrium constants	Turnover number, min^{-1}
$[\text{IrCl}_5(\text{OH})]^{2-}$	1.2×10^7	1.5
$[\text{IrCl}_4(\text{OH}_2)]^2$	2.8×10^6	1.6
$[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{OH}_3)]^{2-}$	1.1×10^6	3.1
$[\text{IrCl}_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$	1.5×10^5	13.2

x/ Equilibrium constants for the reactions :

The turnover number values for catalytic oxidation reactions of iodide by periodate are also given in Table 2. The data obtained show the dependence of the catalytic activity of a coordination compound on the nature of ligands located in the inner sphere : increasing the number of hydroxyl groups in the inner sphere increases the catalytic activity of complexes.

The dependence of catalytic action on the inner sphere complex composition is one of the most characteristic features of coordination compounds of platinum metals, homogeneous catalysts.

In all reactions studied the presence of chloride in the inner sphere lowered the catalytic activity but the substitution of chloride by water, sulphate-ion and, in particular, by hydroxyl-ion sharply increased the catalytic activity.

Analogous mechanism and regularities have been revealed in studying the catalytic action of ruthenium(III) and ruthenium(IV) compounds in the same reaction²⁵.

If in this reaction one replaces a reductant by organic amines, then the same regularities are observed which point to a decisive part played by the stages involving periodate reduction²⁶.

The investigation of catalytic activity of a mixture of ruthenium and iridium complex ions in the iodide oxidation by periodate has shown that a two-nucleus complex compound with higher catalytic activity compared to the additive value is formed between two complexes of the $[\text{IrCl}_{6-n}(\text{OH})_n]^{2-}$ and $[\text{RuCl}_{6-n}(\text{OH})_n]^{2-}$ types²⁷. One may suppose that in the complex under consideration between iridium and ruthenium atoms a hydroxide bridge is formed.

A great excess of iridium(IV) compounds in solution or long keeping of solution with a mixture of compounds decreases the catalytic activity pointing to the formation of poly-nucleus coordination compounds with low catalytic activity.

It should be noted that a marked interaction between iridium and ruthenium complexes are already observed at their concentration of the order of 10^{-6}M .

The number of investigated redox reactions catalysed by platinum, palladium or rhodium compounds is scarce.

B. Krishna and B. P. Sinha²⁸ have studied the oxidation of thallium(I) salts in solution by cerium(IV) compounds. This reaction is catalysed by platinum(IV) compounds. The authors think that some electro-neutral species PtCl_4 is formed in solution and some reaction stages run by a two-electron mechanism.

Kalinina and Moiseeva²⁹ have found that the reduction of iron(III) compounds by tin(II) salts is catalysed by platinum compounds. This reaction is also catalysed by other compounds of platinum metals.

Homogeneous redox processes catalysed by rhodium and palladium compounds are either unknown or described insufficiently and need further investigation.

Numerous oxidation reactions of different reductants by halogenates (iodate, bromate and chlorate) are known to be catalysed by compounds of such platinum metals as osmium and ruthenium and used for determination of the above metals by their catalytic effect in analytical practice^{30,31}. However, the kinetics and mechanism of these reactions have not been studied in detail and, therefore, are not discussed here.

Recently, I with my co-workers L. P. Tichonova and L. N. Zakrevska³² have started studying "secondary" catalytic effects caused by ruthenium compounds in homogeneous oscillating reactions.

Oscillating reactions are those in which the concentrations of some substances are periodically changed in time (at vigorous agitation of solutions). Such reactions were first opened by B. Belousov³³. They are simplest models of biochemical oscillating processes.

In the oscillating systems studied so far oxidant and reductant (for example, bromate and malonic acid) were present at rather high concentration and one-electron redox pair (for example, cerium(IV)-cerium(III), manganese(III)-manganese(II), etc.) at much lower concentration (by 1-2 orders of magnitude). Since in the oscillating reaction the total concentration of the above redox pair is not changed, this pair may be regarded as a catalyst and the oscillating reaction itself as an original catalytic process. The essence of the oscillating reaction registered consists in repeated transitions of a catalyst ("initial" catalyst) from one state into another state.

It was of interest to affect chemically, catalytically one of the stages of the oscillating reaction, namely, the interaction of an initial catalyst with a substrate, i.e. to realize second order catalytic effect. As mentioned, the reaction between cerium(IV) or manganese(III) and some reductants is catalysed by sulphate ruthenium(III,IV) complexes.

Therefore, two oscillating systems described in the literature were taken for investigation, namely, bromate-cerium(III,IV)-malonic acid and bromate-manganese(II,III)-malonic acid. The former has been studied in detail. Noyes and Field³⁷ proposed the mechanism of this process as ten consecutive reactions. As one of the reactions (the interaction of cerium(IV) with malonic acid) may be catalysed by ruthenium compounds, then changes in the oscilla-

ting process may be expected on introduction of ruthenium compounds into solution, and, in particular, shortening of time of the oxidation of malonic acid or its derivatives by cerium(IV).

The changes that took place in the oscillating system were registered by a spectrophotometer with an automatic device to measure the concentration of cerium(IV) in the first case (optical density at $\lambda = 400$ nm) and manganese(III) in the second case ($\lambda = 510$ nm). The reaction was run in 3N H_2SO_4 at 25° and vigorous agitation. At the moment of solution mixing a stop-watch was started. The optical density was measured for 20 min.

Fig. 4 shows how variations in cerium(IV) concentration are changed in the first system in the presence of ruthenium sulphate complexes. It also presents the concentrations for the tests performed. It should be noted that the concentration of ruthenium complexes was two orders of magnitude lower than that of "initial" catalyst, cerium(III,IV) compounds.

Fig. 4. The influence of ruthenium (III, IV) sulphate compounds on the oscillating process in the bromate-cerium-malonic acid system.

Fig. 4 shows that the addition of ruthenium compounds does not much influence the oscillation amplitude, but appreciably increases the oscillation frequency, in which, in fact, the secondary catalytic effect experimentally observed lies.

An analogous, though much low secondary catalytic effect of ruthenium compounds was observed in the second oscillating system (bromate-manganese(II,III)-malonic acid).

Fig. 5 presents the dependence of oscillation frequency in both systems on the concentration of ruthenium(III,IV) compounds.

Fig. 5. Reagent concentration : KBrO_3 —0.033M, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3$, 0.001 M, H_2SO_4 —1.5 M.

1—in the absence of ruthenium compounds ; 2 and 3—the concentration of ruthenium compounds 3×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} , respectively.

Fig. 5. The dependence of oscillation frequency (in hertz) on ruthenium(III, IV) concentration in the two systems : 1-bromate-cerium(III, IV)-malonic acid- H_2SO_4 ; 2-bromate-manganese(II, III)—malonic acid— H_2SO_4 .

It follows from Fig. 4 that the major changes in the oscillation parameters in the presence of ruthenium(III,IV) compounds take place in the period of cerium(IV) consumption. The reduction of cerium(IV) in this period according to⁷⁷ proceeds as follows :

We have examined the influence of ruthenium-(III,IV) compounds on the rate of cerium(IV) and manganese(III) reductions by malonic acid and found that with in the concentration range of ruthenium compounds from 10^{-6} to 10^{-5} M the rate of these reactions increases.

While investigating the first oscillation system, all researchers observed an induction period, the time required to reach oscillation conditions.

In our tests we also observed induction periods in the first and second systems about 240 and 190 sec respectively. Addition of ruthenium compounds in small quantities sharply reduced the length of an induction period, Fig. 6. Such an effect of ruthenium compounds may be due to their catalytic action in one

or some redox reactions that occur in the induction period³⁷.

Fig. 6. The dependence of the length of induction period the ruthenium(III, IV) concentration : in the two systems : 1-bromate-cerium(III, IV)-malonic acid-1.5 M H S. 2—bromate-manganese(II, III)-malonic acid-1.5 H_2SO_4 .

The addition of a greater amount of ruthenium compounds (10^{-5} M) to solution leads to still greater changes in the second oscillation system (a new induction period appears, etc.)

Kinetics and mechanism of homogeneous redox processes catalysed by compounds of platinum metals have been investigated for some years. The data obtained, in our opinion, are of interest and may be helpful both in theory and practice. They have already found application in analytical chemistry : trace quantities of platinum metals in solution can be determined by means of the catalytic effects described. The action of platinum elements at microconcentrations on the oscillation reactions may suggest possible schemes of participation of microelements in physiological processes.

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Abbreviations

- DAN SSSR* — Doklady Acad. Nauk SSSR—Proceed. of Acad. of Sci. of USSR (russ).
- TEKh* — Theoretical and experimental chemistry (russ).
- ZhNKh* — Zhurnal neorganicheskoi khimii—Journal inorganic chem. (russ.)
- ZhAKh* — Zhurnal analyticheskoi khimii—Journal Anal. Chem. (russ).